

Synthesis of some 1-{2-(phthalimido-*N*-oxy)-ethyl} derivatives of 4-(4-substituted phenyl)-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydro-3,5-bis-*N*-(4-oxo-2-phenylquinazolin-3(4*H*))-ylcarboxamides

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Abstract : A series of 1-{2-(phthalimido-*N*-oxy)-ethyl}-4-(4-substituted phenyl)-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydro-3,5-bis-*N*-(4-oxo-2-phenylquinazolin-3(4*H*))-ylcarboxamides (6a-d) have been synthesized via a multistep reaction sequence. Ethyl acetoacetate, various aldehydes and ammonia were condensed in ethanol to yield diethyl 4-(4-substituted phenyl)-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate (2a-d). Ester group of these 2a-d was replaced by hydrazine hydrate in dioxane to give 4-(4-substituted phenyl)-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarbohydrazide (3a-d). These were further treated with benzoxazine-4(3*H*)-one to give 4-(4-substituted phenyl)-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydro-3,5-bis-*N*-(4-oxo-2-phenylquinazolin-3(4*H*))-ylcarboxamides (4a-d). Final compounds 6a-d were obtained by refluxing 4a-d with bromoethoxyphthalimide (5). The structures of the synthesized compounds were assigned on the basis of elemental analysis, IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral data.

Keywords : Ethyl acetoacetate, 1,4-dihydropyridine, aldehydes, phthalimidoxethyl bromide derivative.

Introduction

The pharmacological 1,4-DHPs derivatives are at the eve of a novel boom. Substituted 1,4-dihydropyridines^{1,2} are well-known as calcium channel blockers and have emerged as important classes of drugs for the treatment of hypertension³. 1,4-DHPs classes of compounds are excellent starting synthons for development of antitubercular agents⁴⁻⁶. Newly synthesized generations of 1,4-DHPs possess different pharmacological activities such as anticancer⁷, antidiabetic⁸, antianginal⁹, bronchodilating¹⁰, neurotropic¹¹, antiallergic¹², anti-inflammatory¹³, acaricidal, insecticidal, bactericidal, herbicidal¹⁴ and other pharmacological activities¹⁵. These are used extensively in the treatment of angina pectoris, and arrhythmia¹⁶ and some cardiovascular disorder. Several new derivatives of 1,4-DHP have been prepared and pharmacologically evaluated in order to find drugs with better pharmacological properties¹⁷. In recent years there has been an increased interest in the chemistry of quinazoline-4(3*H*)-ones because of their biological significance. Many of them show antifungal¹⁸, antibacterial¹⁹, anticancer²⁰, anti-

inflammatory²¹, anticonvulsant²², immunotropic²³, hypolipidemic²⁴, antitumor²⁵, antiulcer²⁶, analgesic²⁷ and antiproliferative²⁸ activities as well as inhibitory effects for thymidylate synthase²⁹, and poly(ADP-ribose) polymerase (PARP)³⁰. Several derivatives of alkoxyphthalimide have been synthesized^{31,32} by our research group and reported to demonstrate a wide range of pharmacological activities viz. anticancer, antimalarial, antimicrobial etc.^{33,34}.

Results and discussion

Substituted aromatic aldehydes 1a-d and liquor ammonia were allowed to react with double mole of ethyl acetoacetate in ethanol, when cyclization occurred, resulting in the formation of 2a-d characterized by IR and ¹H NMR spectral data. The IR spectra of compounds 2a-d showed an intense band at 3329 cm⁻¹ for NH moiety of the dihydropyridine ring. The ¹H NMR spectra of these compounds displayed singlet for NH proton at δ 8.81 and one singlet at δ 2.6 due to methyl group of pyridine ring. The triplet at δ 1.3 accounted for CH₃ proton and quartet

for CH₂ proton at δ 3.7 (O-CH₂CH₃). Treatment of **2a-d** with double moles of hydrazine hydrate in dioxane furnished **3a-d**. Formation of **3a-d** was confirmed by the presence of N-H stretching band at 3328–3268 cm⁻¹. Treatment of **3a-d** with double moles of quinazoline-4(3H)-ones and catalytic amount of pyridine gave **4a-d** which was confirmed by a sharp peak at 1693 of C=O and 1653 cm⁻¹ due to C=N stretching in IR region. Treatment of **4a-d** with bromoethoxyphthalimide (**5**) in DMF using TEA as a base afforded 1-{2-(phthalimido-N-oxy)-ethyl}-4-(4-substituted phenyl)-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydro-3,5-bis-N-(4-oxo-2-phenylquinazolin-3(4H)-yl)carboxamides (**6a-d**). These compounds were characterized by new band for C=O of CO-N-CO at 1741–1694 cm⁻¹ and appearance of new signals for N-O and C-O bond at 1373 and 1091 cm⁻¹ respectively in IR spectra. In ¹H NMR spectra disappearance of NH signal at δ 8.83 and presence of two new triplets for NCH₂ and OCH₂ group at δ 3.75 and 4.45 respectively of the ethyl side chain also helped in assigning the structure of **6a-d**. Formations of **6a-d** were also supported by the positive chemical test (fluorescence test) characteristic for the phthalimidoxy group. Compounds **6a-d** were also verified by their N analysis and MS fragmentation pattern data.

Experimental

Melting points of all synthesized compounds were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 1300 FT IR spectrometer and ¹H NMR were determined on a Bruker WM-400 (400 MHz FT NMR) spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. Mass spectra were recorded on Jeol D-300 (EI) and Jeol Sx-102 (FAB) spectrometer. Purity of compounds was checked by elemental analysis and TLC using silica gel-G as adsorbent and visualization was accomplished with iodine. Compound **5** was synthesized by reported methods³⁵. Physical and analytical data are given in Table 1.

Synthesis of diethyl 4-(4-chlorophenyl)-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate (2a) : To a solution of aromatic aldehyde (0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 mL), ethyl acetoacetate (0.02 mol) and liquor ammonia (2.5 mL) were added. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 h and the solid obtained was collected and filtered. It was washed with cold ethanol and recrystallised from ethanol.

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3329 (N-H str.), 3058 (C-H str. Ar-H), 2984 (C-H str. CH₃), 1043 (C-O str.), 1742 (C=O str.), 776 (C-Cl str.); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 8.81 (1H, s, NH), 6.8–7.1 (4H, m, Ar-H), 4.9 (1H, s, Ar-CH), 3.7 (4H, q, -CH₂), 2.6 (6H, s, CH₃), 1.3 (6H, t, CH₃).

Compounds **2b-d** were also prepared by similar methods with some change in reflux time and reaction work up. Their characteristic spectral and analytical data are given below :

Diethyl 2,6-dimethyl-4-phenyl-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate (2b) :

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3327 (N-H str.), 3054 (C-H str. Ar-H), 2981 (C-H str. CH₃), 1028 (C-O str.), 1740 (C=O str.); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 8.78 (1H, s, NH), 6.7–6.9 (5H, m, Ar-H), 4.6 (1H, s, Ar-CH), 3.4 (4H, q, -CH₂), 2.4 (6H, s, CH₃), 1.4 (6H, t, CH₃).

Diethyl 4-(4-fluorophenyl)-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate (2c) :

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3331 (N-H str.), 3062 (C-H str. Ar-H), 2986 (C-H str. CH₃), 1048 (C-O str.), 1743 (C=O str.), 1232 (C-F str.); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 8.87 (1H, s, NH), 6.9–7.4 (4H, m, Ar-H), 5.1 (1H, s, Ar-CH), 3.9 (4H, q, -CH₂), 2.8 (6H, s, CH₃), 1.4 (6H, t, CH₃).

Diethyl 4-(4-methoxyphenyl)-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate (2d) :

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3329 (N-H str.), 3056 (C-H str. Ar-H), 2981 (C-H str. CH₃), 1032 (C-O str.), 1746 (C=O str.); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 8.81 (1H, s, NH), 6.8–7.1 (4H, m, Ar-H), 4.9 (1H, s, Ar-CH), 3.83 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.7 (4H, q, -CH₂), 2.6 (6H, s, CH₃), 1.3 (6H, t, CH₃).

Synthesis of 4-(4-chlorophenyl)-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarbohydrazide (3a) : A mixture of **2a** (0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.02 mol) in dioxane (25 mL) were refluxed for 8 h over sand bath. The mixture was concentrated by distillation under reduced pressure. The concentrated mixture was poured over crushed ice. The solid formed was recrystallised from ethanol.

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3328–3268 (N-H str.), 3068 (C-H str. Ar-H), 2973 (C-H str. CH₃), 1684 (C=O str.), 752 (C-Cl str.); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 9.2 (1H, s, NH), 8.09 (1H, s, CONH), 6.8–7.1 (4H, m, Ar-H), 5.6 (1H, s, Ar-CH), 4.9 (4H, s, NH₂), 2.8 (6H, s, CH₃).

Note

DMF/TEA 5

	a	b	c	d
X =	Cl	H	F	OCH ₃

Reaction Scheme

Table 1. Physical and analytical data of synthesized compounds

Compd.	Mol. formula	Mol. weight	X	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	N (%)	
						Found/(Calcd.)	
2a	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ ClNO ₄	363.83	Cl	153	92	3.78 (3.84)	
2b	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ NO ₄	329.39	H	119	90	4.19 (4.25)	
2c	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ FNO ₄	347.38	F	121	89	3.96 (4.03)	
2d	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ NO ₅	359.41	OCH ₃	127	91	3.84 (3.89)	
3a	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ ClN ₅ O ₂	335.78	Cl	124	85	20.80 (20.84)	
3b	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₂	301.34	H	146	83	23.19 (23.22)	
3c	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ FN ₅ O ₂	301.34	F	142	81	21.89 (21.92)	
3d	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₃	331.36	OCH ₃	149	80	12.09 (12.12)	
4a	C ₄₃ H ₃₂ ClN ₇ O ₄	745.21	Cl	84	78	13.07 (13.13)	
4b	C ₄₃ H ₃₂ N ₇ O ₄	711.76	H	102	76	13.69 (13.76)	
4c	C ₄₃ H ₃₂ FN ₇ O ₄	729.75	F	89	75	13.40 (13.42)	
4d	C ₄₄ H ₃₅ N ₇ O ₅	741.79	OCH ₃	87	77	13.18 (13.21)	
6a	C ₅₃ H ₃₉ ClN ₈ O ₇	935.37	Cl	119	71	11.90 (11.97)	
6b	C ₅₃ H ₃₉ N ₈ O ₇	900.93	H	127	68	12.39 (12.43)	
6c	C ₅₃ H ₃₉ FN ₈ O ₇	918.92	F	108	70	12.39 (12.18)	
6d	C ₅₄ H ₄₂ N ₈ O ₈	930.96	OCH ₃	117	65	11.96 (12.03)	

Similarly, compounds 3b-d were also prepared with some change in reflux time and reaction work up. Their characteristic spectral and analytical data are given below :

2,6-Dimethyl-4-phenyl-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarbohydrazide (3b) :

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3321–3258 (N-H str.), 3064 (C-H str. Ar-H), 2969 (C-H str. CH₃), 1690 (C=O str.); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 8.11 (1H, s, CONH), 8.9 (1H, s, NH), 6.9 (5H, m, Ar-H), 6.5–5.1 (4H, s, NH₂), 5.4 (1H, s, Ar-CH), 2.3 (6H, s, CH₃).

4-(4-Fluorophenyl)-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarbohydrazide (3c) :

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3331–3273 (N-H str.), 3074 (C-H str. Ar-H), 2968 (C-H str. CH₃), 1691 (C=O str.), 1198 (C-F str.); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 9.4 (1H, s, NH), 8.15 (1H, s, CONH), 6.9–7.4 (4H, m, Ar-H), 5.9 (1H, s, Ar-CH), 5.0 (4H, s, NH₂), 2.8 (6H, s, CH₃).

4-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarbohydrazide (3d) : IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3328–3268 (N-H str.), 3068 (C-H str. Ar-H), 2973 (C-H str. CH₃), 1694 (C=O str.), 752 (C-Cl str.); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 9.1 (1H, s, NH), 8.13 (2H, s, CONH), 6.5–6.8 (4H, m, Ar-H), 5.6 (1H, s, Ar-CH), 4.7 (4H, s, NH₂), 3.79 (3H, s, OCH₃), 2.6 (6H, s, CH₃).

Synthesis of 4-(4-chlorophenyl)-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydro-3,5-bis-N-(4-oxo-2-phenyl quinazolin-3(4H)-ylcarboxamides (4a) : A mixture of 3a (0.01 mol) and 2-phenyl-4H-3,1-benzoxazin-4-one (0.02 mol) in ethanol was added to it with a catalytic amount of pyridine. Reaction mixture was refluxed for 8 h and poured on crushed ice. The solid obtained was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3356–3247 (N-H str.), 3060 (C-H str. Ar-H), 2984 (C-H str. CH₃), 1693 (C=O str.), 1653 (C=N str.), 747 (C-Cl str.); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 8.83 (1H, s, NH), 7.38 (1H, s, CONH), 7.1–8.57 (4H, m, Ar-H), 4.8 (1H, s, Ar-CH), 2.25 (6H, s, CH₃).

Compounds 4b-d were prepared in similar way with minor changes in reflux time.

2,6-Dimethyl-1,4-dihydro-3,5-bis-N-(4-oxo-2-phenylquinazolin-3(4H)-ylcarboxamides (4b) :

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3354–3243 (N-H str.) 3058 (C-H str. Ar-H), 2983 (C-H str. CH₃), 1691 (C=O str.), 1651 (C=N str.); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 8.62 (1H, s, NH), 7.32 (1H, s, CONH), 7.0–8.52 (5H, m, Ar-H), 4.6 (1H, s, Ar-CH), 2.23 (6H, s, CH₃).

4-(4-Fluorophenyl)-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydro-3,5-bis-N-(4-oxo-2-phenylquinazolin-3(4H)-ylcarboxamides (4c) :

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3358–3249 (N-H str.), 3063 (C-H

str. Ar-H), 2987 (C-H str. CH₃), 1694 (C=O str.), 1657 (C=N str.), 1176 (C-F str.); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 8.91 (1H, s, NH), 7.37 (1H, s, CONH), 7.3-8.59 (4H, m, Ar-H), 5.6 (1H, s, Ar-CH), 2.28 (6H, s, CH₃).

4-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydro-3,5-bis-N-(4-oxo-2-phenylquinazolin-3(4H)-ylcarboxamides (4d) :

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3357-3248 (N-H str.), 3061 (C-H str. Ar-H), 2982 (C-H str. CH₃), 1693 (C=O str.), 1656 (C=N str.), 1094 (C-O str.); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 8.74 (1H, s, NH), 7.34 (1H, s, CONH), 7.2-8.55 (4H, m, Ar-H), 4.7 (1H, s, Ar-CH), 3.81 (3H, s, OCH₃), 2.24 (6H, s, CH₃).

Synthesis of 1-{2-(phthalimido-N-oxy)-ethyl}-4-(4-chlorophenyl)-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydro-3,5-bis-N-(4-oxo-2-phenylquinazolin-3(4H)-ylcarboxamides (6a) :

Compound **4a** (0.01 mol) and TEA in DMF, phthalimidoxethylbromide **5** (0.01 mol) was added portionwise and refluxed for 12 h, it was cooled and poured into crushed ice. The solid obtained was filtered and recrystallized from ethanol.

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3366 (N-H str.), 3060 (C-H str. Ar-H), 2984 (C-H str. CH₃), 1693 (C=O str.), 1653 (C=N str), 747 (C-Cl str.); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 7.13 (1H, s, CONH), 7.2-8.5 (26H, m, Ar-H), 4.83 (1H, s, Ar-CH), 4.45 (2H, t, OCH₂), 3.75 (2H, t, NCH₂), 2.25 (6H, s, CH₃); MS : *m/z* 934 [M]⁺, 936 [M+2]⁺.

Same procedure was adopted for the synthesis of compounds **6b-d**. Their spectral data are given below :

1-{2-(Phthalimido-N-oxy)-ethyl}-4-phenyl)-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydro-3,5-bis-N-(4-oxo-2-phenylquinazolin-3(4H)-ylcarboxamides (6b) :

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3359 (N-H str.), 3054 (C-H str. Ar-H), 2981 (C-H str. CH₃), 1690 (C=O str.), 1651 (C=N str.); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 7.11 (1H, s, CONH), 7.0-8.2 (27H, m, Ar-H), 4.81 (1H, s, Ar-CH), 4.42 (2H, t, OCH₂), 3.67 (2H, t, NCH₂) 2.23 (6H, s, CH₃); MS : *m/z* 900 [M]⁺.

1-{2-(Phthalimido-N-oxy)-ethyl}-4-(4-fluorophenyl)-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydro-3,5-bis-N-(4-oxo-2-phenylquinazolin-3(4H)-ylcarboxamides (6c) :

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3368 (N-H str.), 3064 (C-H str. Ar-H), 2989 (C-H str. CH₃), 1697 (C=O str.), 1658 (C=N str), 1187 (C-F str.); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 7.17 (1H,

s, CONH), 7.5-8.8 (26H, m, Ar-H), 4.88 (1H, s, Ar-CH), 4.46 (2H, t, OCH₂), 3.78 (2H, t, NCH₂), 2.34 (6H, s, CH₃); MS : *m/z* 918 [M]⁺.

1-{2-(Phthalimido-N-oxy)-ethyl}-4-(4-methoxyphenyl)-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydro-3,5-bis-N-(4-oxo-2-phenylquinazolin-3(4H)-ylcarboxamides (6d) :

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3356 (N-H str.), 3054 (C-H str. Ar-H), 2982 (C-H str. CH₃), 1693 (C=O str.), 1651 (C=N str), 1087 (C-O str.); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 7.14 (1H, s, CONH), 7.4-8.7 (26H, m, Ar-H), 4.80 (1H, s, Ar-CH), 4.43 (2H, t, OCH₂), 3.67 (2H, t, NCH₂), 3.82 (3H, s, OCH₃), 2.24 (6H, s, CH₃); MS : *m/z* 930[M]⁺.

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